

ISSN: 2181-4562

DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4562

IMFAKTOR

JOCAA

VOLUME I, ISSUE 8

МАДАНИЯТ ВА САНЪАТ

JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО

OCTOBER

2023

ISSN: 2181-4562
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4562

МАДАНИЯТ ВА САЊАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

I-ЖИЛД, 8-СОҢ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО

ТОМ-I, НОМЕР-8

JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

VOLUME-I, ISSUE-8

ТОШКЕНТ – 2023

МАДАНИЯТ ВА САНЪАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО | JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

№ 8 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.56017/2181-4562-2023-8>

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“Маданият ва санъат” журнали 2023 йил 24 февраль куни № 065356-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган. Мазкур журнал **6 та** халқаро маълумотлар базаларида индексланган бўлиб, жорий йил учун **UIF 2023 = 7.7 “импакт-фактор”** кўрсаткичига эга.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий таълим, фан ва инновациялар вазирлиги ҳузуридаги Олий аттестация комиссиясининг 2023 йил 24 июлдаги 01-02/1199-сонли хатига мувофиқ ушбу журналда чоп этилган мақолалар **хорижий мақолалар сифатида тан олинади.**

Саҳифаловчи\Page Maker\Верстка: Абдурахмон Хасанов

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МАДАНИЯТ ВА САЊАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО | JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

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ACTING – AS THE MAIN TOOL OF SELF-EXPRESSION OF A SINGER-ARTIST

ANNOTATION

Acting is the main weapon of a singer-artist in the integrity of the performance of works and winning the hearts of the audience. Acting classes in vocal groups are not aimed at mastering the skills of the acting profession, but at developing the psychophysical aspect of the future artist, thanks to which he learns to open up to the world and gets rid of fears associated with communicating with other people and performing in front of an audience. This article discusses the role of acting in the artist's activity, and also provides several exercises as a way of liberation both physically and psycho-emotionally.

Key words: Acting, vocals, imagery, singing voice, emotionality, expressiveness, sensuality, education, curriculum, talent.

АКТЁРСКОЕ МАСТЕРСТВО – КАК ГЛАВНОЕ ОРУДИЕ САМОВЫРАЖЕНИЕ ПЕВЦА-АРТИСТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Актерское мастерство является главным оружием певца-артиста в целостности исполнения произведений и завоевании сердец зрителей. Занятия по актёрскому мастерству в вокальных коллективах направлены не на освоение навыков профессии актера, а на развитие психофизического аспекта будущего артиста, благодаря которому он учится раскрываться миру, избавляется от страхов, связанных с общением с другими людьми, выступлением перед публикой. В данной статье обсуждается роль актёрского мастерства в деятельности артиста, так же даны несколько упражнений как способ физически и психоэмоционально раскрепощений.

Ключевые слова: актёрское мастерство, вокал, образность, певческий голос, эмоциональность, выразительность, чувственность, образование, учебная программа, талант.

AKTYORLIK - ASOSIY VOSITA SIFATIDA QO'SHIQCHI-RASSOMNING O'ZINI NAMOYON QILISHI

ANNOTATSIYA

Aktyorlik-bu qo'shiqchi-artistning asarlarning yaxlitligi va tomoshabinlar qalbini zabt etishdagi asosiy quroli. Aktyorlik darslari vokal jamoalarida ular aktyor kasbi ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga emas, balki kelajakdagi rassomning psixofizik jihatini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan bo'lib, buning natijasida u o'zini dunyoga ochib berishni o'rganadi, boshqa odamlar bilan muloqot qilish, omma oldida chiqish bilan bog'liq qo'rquvlardan xalos bo'ladi. Ushbu maqolada aktyorning rassom faoliyatidagi roli muhokama qilinadi, shuningdek, jismoniy va psixo-emotsional ravishda ozod qilish usuli sifatida bir nechta mashqlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: aktyorlik, vokal, obrazlilik, qo'shiq ovozi, hissiyotlilik, ekspressivlik, shahvoniylik, ta'lim, o'quv dasturi, iste'dod.

INTRODUCTION

A singer is an actor who uses the singing voice as an instrument. Each musical phrase tells a story, which is also conveyed through body language, facial expressions, diction and vocal dynamics. In modern society, it is difficult for people to feel liberated, manage their emotions, communicate freely, and be confident. Most feel fear, aggression, uncertainty, and cannot express their thoughts and feelings. Emotional depression leads to internal pressures, which manifest themselves not only in facial expressions and speech, but also in movements. Acting classes help solve these problems.

Acting abilities, in a broad sense, are the skills and abilities of arbitrary performance of roles, imitation of someone's behavior, depiction of certain feelings, experiences, relationships, etc.; in a narrow sense - the competence of an actor.

Acting classes in vocal groups are not aimed at mastering the skills of the acting profession, but at developing the psychophysical aspect of the future artist, thanks to which he learns to open up to the world and gets rid of fears associated with communicating with other people and performing in front of an audience. The curriculum in this subject contributes to the development and improvement of students' communication skills, the ability to work in a group, the development of organizational abilities and leadership qualities, and readiness for creative activity.

METHODS AND METHODOLOGY

Unfortunately, the fear of speaking in front of an audience is a common phenomenon among people of different ages and social statuses. It deprives us of many of the joys of life, but we can fight it, for example, with the help of acting. This does not mean that you need to apply makeup to those around you or gesticulate wildly; there are more effective techniques.

Acting is the professional activity of an actor, the ability to transform into a hero and act on his behalf in a performance. When a specialist prepares for a role, he uses makeup, costumes, masks and other items. This helps him transform externally. But in order to convey the character's image as accurately as possible and influence the viewer, this is not enough. The artist connects internal mechanisms - physical (body, plasticity, speech, motor skills) and psychological (emotionality, imagination, memory).

In order to organically grasp the meaning before learning the musical material and give consistency to the learning process, you can use not only a detailed analysis of the text of the role and libretto, familiarity with the concept and history of creation, but also do a number of practical exercises that allow you to assimilate the true meaning of what is happening to the character. One such effective exercise is a sketch with a partner on the theme of a piece or episode from the opera that you are working on.

To do this, students are given the task of acting out a passage in the proposed circumstances of the opera and using their words to model the situation and conflict. After showing the independent work, together with the director-teacher, the effective meaning of the passage is determined, the partners must understand why and for what purpose certain lines are born. If there is a clear understanding of what I want to achieve from my partner, then the text of the vocal part can be safely learned.

Exercises - etudes are available for independent work by students, since the course on the fundamentals of acting (which is part of the curriculum) provides practical acquaintance with the etude method. Of course, if the exercises are carried out under the supervision of an acting teacher, then the correct result will appear faster.

The etude method can be successfully carried out in the conditions of study at a university, but in further practical work in the theater this is hardly possible, since theatrical practice gravitates towards routine and is based on the fact that a trained person has his own individual baggage of skill, knows the methodology for working on a role and way. This reasoning is controversial, but partly true. And if, in the conditions of studying at a university, a student comprehends the meaning of effective analysis of a text with the help of analysis and sketch, then in the future, in practical work, he will be able to successfully deal with verbal action and text in the conditions of homework on a role.

Working on the meaning and content of solo pieces requires the same detailed analysis of the text. But, unlike duet episodes, here it is necessary to more carefully work out the line of internal visions. The birth of inner visions is influenced by both text and music, which excites creative imagination. It is important that these visions help to find the exact action, since students pay their attention primarily to the feelings that arise at one time or another, under the influence of music. But we must remember that the feelings that surround us are aimed at achieving a certain goal. If such an understanding arises in a student during the period of study, then in the future he will not choke on his own tears, fall into "creative hysteria", the energy of singing and acting will be balanced.

This technique of consolidating the logic of feelings with the logic of actions is also a tool for the vocalist. Music depicts to us feelings, moods of characters, the logic of the development of passions, and we listen to them carefully and analyze their meaning. According to Stanislavsky, the singer-actor must learn to perform a "sensual analysis" of a musical work [1, P.47].

This term is not used in the art of dramatic theater; there the term "effective analysis" is used. But, bearing in mind the above, "sensory analysis" most accurately determines the way of working on a role in opera. In practice, this suggests that in the event of questions arising regarding the logic of an action or discrepancies with the meaning, the singer-actor must choose the following technique for himself as a mechanism for analysis: a feeling, a state, is extracted from the music in order to use them to find the actions characteristic of this state. The action should be determined not only by the text, but also to a much greater extent by the musical score.

The issue of diction, pronunciation and articulation is closely related to verbal action and characterization. Diction should not be perceived by students as a technical aid in mastering the profession of a singer-actor, since this is a more complex psychological process. This process becomes clear and is revealed in detail at the moment of mastering the role, working on the passage. For many, it is not immediately obvious that words are "not read" by the public when the actor does not need them, when the singer-actor does not understand their effective meaning.

It is significant that K.S. Stanislavsky, who deeply knew the laws of music, often repeated that notes, along with words, carry a deep meaning, so you need to sing not sounds, but "mental notes." And along with this, it is necessary to use internal visions so that the imagery of the sounding word increases. "I don't see what you're singing about!" - this is how the great reformer of the stage spoke at rehearsals in the opera studio, referring to the visual images born to the performer on stage [2, P.237].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Acting is of interest not only to actors, directors and other cultural figures. Ordinary people whose profession is not related to the world of theater and cinema also want to master it.

Acting is useful and helps:

- to feel yourself confident;
- manage your emotions;
- liberate yourself and go beyond the usual;
- develop empathy;
- speak competently and beautifully;
- develop public speaking skills;
- find a new profession (acting allows you to try on any role);
- better control of your body;
- train memory;
- plunge into creativity and make your life brighter.

When a person acquires new skills, it is easier for him to do something that he could not decide on before.

To combat tightness, the actor has various techniques in his toolkit. For example:

An exercise in public solitude

- Helps overcome fear when meeting new people or performing. Its essence is to begin to interact with people and “voluntarily-forcedly” find yourself in the center of attention.

You can go outside where there are a lot of people and start singing or reading a poem, or go into a store and talk very loudly. This will draw attention to you and put you in a stressful situation. It is very important to overcome yourself and complete the exercise to the end.

Exercise “I am in the proposed circumstances”

This exercise develops imagination, helps to try on different roles, understand yourself and others. This technique uses the “If only...” principle. You need to answer the questions: “If I were born and raised in these circumstances, communicated with such and such people, had certain opportunities, dressed and spoke like another specific person, then what would I do?” In this way you can put yourself in the place of another.

Exercise helps you become more confident in important negotiations and meetings. You give yourself the attitude: “If I were a first-class coach/lawyer/manager, this is how I would behave.” And you demonstrate the behavior of a successful person.

Exercise “Tongue Twisters”

A person’s voice is his calling card, which can say a lot about his character. In acting, great importance is given to voice production and exercises aimed at developing the speech apparatus. Tongue twisters develop diction well. To make it more difficult, you can speak with a bottle cap in your teeth.

Acting skills are relevant among actors and stage performers, but also for various specialists such as doctors, journalists, psychologists, entrepreneurs, teachers, politicians, musicians, scientists, lawyers, translators, programmers, managers, sellers, drivers and representatives of other professions.

CONCLUSION

Acting helps not only in professional activities, but also in everyday life. It’s not about the ability to pretend, but about the ability to freely communicate with people, understand them, and develop charisma and self-confidence.

For various reasons, the curricula of higher musical educational institutions neglect the importance of the mutual influence of acting and vocal skills. The small number of training hours in the disciplines of “stage speech” and “acting”, their isolation from practical work in the opera class cause irreparable damage to the educational process. As a result, graduate students, entering the theater, philharmonic society, or concert organization, are forced to enter the profession without the necessary set of skills and abilities.

In our opinion, work in the vocal class, where the entire range of skills of the future singer-actor is in demand, should be continuously carried out in parallel with the discipline of “acting” and “stage speech” right up to state exams, which will allow students to develop and strengthen the skills of effective existence on stage.

The idea expressed by the famous opera director and teacher B.A. Pokrovsky is relevant to this day: “Conservatory students preparing to become opera singers are practically deprived of the opportunity to receive any serious education in the spirit of the Stanislavsky system. These results are disastrous for the development of modern opera houses” [3].

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ISSN: 2181-4562
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4562

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JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

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Муассис: «IMFAKTOR Pages» масъулияти чекланган жамияти.

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